

DURABILITY OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY STIFFENED PANELS
UNDER CYCLIC POSTBUCKLING COMPRESSION LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The following study presents an investigation into the capability of flat stiffened composite panels to sustain repeated axial compression loads far in excess of their initial buckling loads. The panels were made of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy tape (0.135 mm per ply). Each panel consisted of a basic skin of 12 plies, integrally stiffened by four equally spaced stiffeners of either "I" or "J" shape. Both types of stiffeners had a web of 12 plies and a cap of 24 plies. Panels were tested to 250000 cycles at increasing load levels, the highest level being close to the static limit load of the panels. The panels were then loaded to failure. Failure occurred at the stiffener's cap and spread to the panel. Manufacturing defects were shown to have some effect on the final failure. Analytical prediction of buckling was obtained using the MSC NASTRAN computer program.

INTRODUCTION

Metallic stiffened panels are widely used in aircraft and ship design. One of their main features is the capability to withstand loads far in excess of their initial buckling loads. Recent studies with stiffened metal shear panels [1], have shown that these panels are susceptible to premature fatigue failure. They could however be successfully used and allow significant weight saving provided that sufficient fatigue data was available.

Composite stiffened panels have recently been introduced in aircraft structures but thus far these structures have been designed not to buckle within the flight envelope loads. This approach reflects the concern with the capability of composite panels to sustain postbuckling loads in static and fatigue loading. The behaviour of composite shear panels has been

investigated in [2-5]. Recent studies [6] with composite shear panels under cyclic post buckling loading have shown their potential and advantage over metallic panels with respect to fatigue sensitivity. The behavior of stiffened composite panels under static compression has been investigated in [5] and [7]. In [7] it was reported that panels held as much as three and a half times their initial buckling load and that failure was initiated in a skin-stiffener interface region.

This paper presents an experimental investigation of graphite/epoxy integrally stiffened flat panels loaded in cyclic compression in the "deep" postbuckling regime. Each panel had either I or J shaped stiffeners. One panel of each type was tested statically to failure and the rest were cycled to at least 250000 cycles and then loaded to failure.

TEST SPECIMENS

Two panel configurations were tested in the present investigation. Both configurations consisted of a flat 12 ply skin and four equally spaced longitudinal stiffeners of either I or J shape, each having a web of 12 plies and a cap of 24 plies. The specimens were fabricated from AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy tape material. This material is a 350°F cure type and is widely used in composite aircraft structures. Thickness per ply of this material is 0.135 mm. Figure 1 shows the geometry and dimensions of the panels and Table 1 summarizes the layup sequence for each type of panel.

Figure 1. Panels geometry and dimensions.

TABLE 1
Panel layup orientation and sequence

Configuration	Skin	Stiffener Web	Stiffener Cap
I Stiffener	$(\pm 45, 0, \pm 45, 90)_S$	$(\pm 45, 90, 0, \pm 45)_S$	$(\pm 45, 0_4, 90, 0_2, \pm 45, 0)_S$
J Stiffener	$(\pm 45, 0, \pm 45, 90)_S$	$(\pm 45, 90, 0, \pm 45)_S$	$(\pm 45, 0_4, 90, 0_2, \pm 45, 0)_S$

0 Orientation denotes plies laid with fibers running longitudinally.

The stiffened panels were designed and fabricated at Israel Aircraft Industries, Engineering Division. The manufacturing process consisted of one curing cycle with the stiffeners integrally laid into the skin and cured with it. All specimens were ultrasonically inspected after curing. Some defects, mainly porosity were detected in the stiffeners and skin under it. These were marked on the specimens and followed during the tests. The ends of each panel were cast into an aluminum U shaped channel, using epoxy, thus giving the panels uniform load distribution along their ends. Uniformity was also ensured by machining the loaded surfaces to be parallel to one another and perpendicular to the panel.

TEST SET UP AND PROCEDURE

Test specimens were instrumented with strain gages bonded back-to-back. These gages were used to detect incipient buckling and to monitor the strains during the tests. Some extra gages were bonded near manufacturing defects to give a warning of their propagation. Displacement gages were used in some of the tests to measure the displacements in the skin and stiffeners. The panels were painted white and the Moire shadow fringe technique was used to record the out-of-plane displacements fringe patterns (see Figure 2). These patterns were recorded using both 35 mm still camera and a television video camera. Testing of the panels was conducted at the Structures Lab., Aeronautical Engineering Department, Technion, Haifa. Three I and three J type stiffened panels were tested in compression using a 50 ton MTS testing machine. One panel of each type was tested statically to failure. The two remaining panels were loaded in cyclic compression to a life goal of 250K cycles. Cyclic loading was applied in blocks of constant amplitude compression at load levels which ranged from 150 percent of the panel initial buckling load to about 2/3 of its ultimate strength (limit load). Preceding each block was a static loading to a level of one ton above the block level. After completion of the cyclic loading the panels were statically loaded to failure in order to determine their residual strength. All tests were conducted at room temperature on specimens which had no moisture conditioning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Skin Buckling

Skin buckling modes of both the I and J stiffened panels had one transverse and five longitudinal half-waves between each pair of stiffeners. Figure 2 shows the wave pattern of panel I2 as obtained by the Moire fringe technique and Figure 3 shows the theoretical wave pattern as computed by finite element analysis.

Experimental initial buckling loads for the skins were determined from plots like those in figures 4 and 5. Buckling was defined as the point of sharp change in the slope of the curve of compression strain as a function of axial load. Buckling load could not be clearly defined from plots of curvature of the skins as a function of compression load (figures 6 and 7). It is worth noticing that the cyclic loading does cause a drop in the rigidity of the panel and hence a steady decrease in the buckling load with increasing number of cycles. A marked difference between the I and J stiffened panels can be observed by comparing the results of figures 4 and 5.

Figure 2. Moiré fringe patterns of skin buckling of panel I2.

Figure 3. Theoretical wave pattern of skin buckling.

Figure 4. Axial compression strains in the skin of panel I2.

Figure 5. Axial Compression strains in the skins of panel J6.

Figure 6. Longitudinal curvature of the skin of panel I2.

Figure 7. Longitudinal curvature of the skin of panel J6.

The axial strain in the skins of the I stiffened panels continues to rise after initial buckling, indicating that the skin continues to carry some additional loads in post buckling. On the other hand, the axial strain in the skins of the J stiffened panels drops somewhat after buckling occurs and then stays more or less constant hence no additional load is being taken by the skin. The drop of strain after buckling can be attributed to the diagonal bending and the small torsional stiffness of the non symmetric J stiffener.

Table 2 summarizes the loading details as well as the results of the buckling and failure loads. The theoretical buckling loads are somewhat higher than the experimental since they represent the bifurcation point values [8].

TABLE 2
Summary of panel loading, buckling and failure loads

Panel Type & Number	Cyclic Load Range [Ton]	Total Number of Cycles	Buckling Loads [Ton]			Failure Loads [Ton]
			Computed	Experimental Before cycling	After 250K cycles	
I 1	Static	-	7.10	5.35	-	24.0
I 2	14-22	315000	7.10	5.80	5.20	32.0
I 3	15-21	250000	7.10	7.00	6.20	33.5
J 4	Static	-	5.15	3.40	-	15.0
J 5	11-12	75000*	5.15	4.50	-	*
J 6	11-15	250000	5.15	6.05	5.00	16.7

* Panel broke during loading due to loading machine failure.

Panel Load Distribution

The strain distribution across the panels was uniform at the start of each test. As the skin approached buckling, its strains began to lag behind those of the stiffeners, indicating an increase in the load carrying share of the stiffeners. This lag effect started in the center between two stiffeners and increased steadily as loading continued deep into the post-buckling regime. Figures 8, 9 show the axial compression strain distribution between two stiffeners and figure 10 shows the change in the distribution caused by the cyclic loading.

Figure 8. Axial compression strain distribution between two stiffeners in panel I2 (P in tons).

Figure 9. Axial compression strain distribution between two stiffeners in panel J4 (P in tons).

The data of figures such as figure 10 (at different load levels, P) was used to define an effective skin width around the stiffeners. Figure 11 shows plots of the effective width as a function of the compression load P at different stages of the cyclic loading. There seems to be a slight increase in the values of b_{eff} after cycling. The values of b_{eff} for the J stiffened panel were lower than those for the I stiffened panel.

Figure 10. Influence of cycling on the axial compression strains in panel I2 (P in tons).

Figure 11. Variations of effective width in panels I2 & J4.

Figure 12. Axial strains in a stiffener of panel I2.

Stiffener Behaviour

The stiffeners in both panel configurations did not buckle during the tests, as can be seen from figures 12 and 13. There was however an increase in bending of the stiffeners due to cyclic loading. Skin buckling caused bending of the webs of the stiffeners as can be seen from figure 14. Cyclic loading of the panel caused the bending to start at a lower load.

Figure 13. Axial curvature in a stiffener of panel I2.

Figure 14. Transverse strains in the web of a stiffener of panel I2.

Figure 15. Typical failure mode, panel I2.

Figure 16. Failure at the location of defects, panel J4.

Effects of Imperfections

Some of the panels included manufacturing defects mainly porosity at the corners between the web and either the flange or the skin. These defects did not affect the initial buckling loads. There were some defects in the caps as well, mostly in panel J4. These also did not affect the initial buckling. Non-destructive inspections during the tests revealed neither initiation of damage nor growth of manufacturing defects due to the cyclic loading. However, final failure loads were affected by manufacturing defects. Geometrical imperfections caused significant variations in the buckling loads as well as in the final failure loads (figure 2).

Final Failure of the Panels

Final failure of all the panels was initiated at the stiffener's caps and spread across the skin along 45 degree lines. A typical failure is shown in figure 15. Panels which contained manufacturing defects in the caps broke at the location of the defects as can be seen in figure 16. No damage or failure occurred at the stiffener-skin interface as was the case in [7]. Final failure load of most panels ranged between 4.4 to 5.5 times their initial buckling load. The fact that the residual strength of the panels is higher after cycling than the strength of the static panels is believed to be due to geometrical variations in the panels and not to "strengthening effect".

CONCLUSIONS

Six integrally stiffened graphite epoxy panels, (three with I shaped stiffeners and 3 with J shaped stiffeners), were tested in the present investigation. All the panels had skin buckling only. The stiffeners continued to carry load until failure. The webs of the stiffeners showed large bending deformations after buckling of the skins but the stiffeners and its caps remained straight.

Buckling loads were unaffected by the presence of manufacturing defects but were greatly influenced by geometrical imperfections. Cyclic loading did not cause any spread of damage or initiation of damage in the panels. There was however some degradation in the stiffness of the panels due to cyclic loads. At this point it is not clear whether this degradation was in the stiffener only or in the entire panel. Tests of stiffeners which are planned for the near future are expected to give some more information about the degradation.

Final failure of all the panels was initiated at the stiffener's caps. The inner stiffeners (of panels with no defects in the caps) failed close to the middle of the panel and the outer stiffeners failed approximately at $1/3$ and $2/3$ of the length of the panel (where the broken 45° fibers which come from the inner stiffeners meet the outer stiffeners). Panels with defects in the caps failed at the location of one of those defects. There was no separation at stiffener-skin interface. Panels carried between 4.4 to 5.5 times their initial buckling load before failing. Residual strength results showed no degradation in the strength of the panels due to fatigue.

The results clearly show that integrally stiffened panels of graphite/epoxy can be designed to buckle below the limit load of the structure thus increasing their weight saving potential.

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